

Video frame interpolation neural network for 3D tomography across different length scales

Laura Gambini^{1,2*}, Cian Gabbett^{1,2}, Luke Doolan^{1,2}, Lewys
Jones^{1,2,3}, Jonathan N. Coleman^{1,2}, Paddy Gilligan⁴
and Stefano Sanvito^{1,2}

¹CRANN Institute and AMBER Centre, Trinity College Dublin,
Dublin 2, Ireland.

²School of Physics, Trinity College Dublin, Dublin 2, Ireland.

³Advanced Microscopy Laboratory, Trinity College Dublin,
Dublin 2, Ireland.

⁴Mater Misericordiae University Hospital, Dublin 7, Ireland.

*Corresponding author. E-mail: gambinil@tcd.ie

Abstract

Three-dimensional (3D) tomography is a powerful investigative tool for many scientific domains, going from materials science, to engineering, to medicine. Many factors may limit the 3D resolution, often spatially anisotropic, compromising the precision of the information retrievable. A neural network, designed for video-frame interpolation, is employed to enhance tomographic images, achieving cubic-voxel resolution. The method is applied to distinct domains: the investigation of the morphology of printed graphene nanosheets networks, obtained via focused ion beam-scanning electron microscope (FIB-SEM), magnetic resonance imaging of the human brain, and X-ray computed tomography scans of the abdomen. The accuracy of the 3D tomographic maps can be quantified through computer-vision metrics, but most importantly with the precision on the physical quantities retrievable from the reconstructions, in the case of FIB-SEM the porosity, tortuosity, and effective diffusivity. This work showcases a versatile image-augmentation strategy for optimizing 3D tomography acquisition conditions, while preserving the information content.

Keywords: FIB-SEM, tomography, graphene, video frame interpolation, RIFE, CT, MRI

1 Introduction

Three-dimensional (3D) tomography refers to a collection of methods used for producing 3D representations of the internal structure of a solid object. This practice is commonly used for the study of specimens, where the material properties are strongly related to their internal structure. The morphology of a sample can be practically defined over many different length scales. A good example in materials science is that of networks of solution-processed nanomaterials, widely employed in electronics, energy, and sensing [1, 2]. For these, the charge transport is determined by the morphology of the contacts between nanosheets, which are defined at a few tens of nanometers length scale. At the opposite side of the length-scale spectrum, one finds medical imaging techniques [3], such as magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) and X-ray computed tomography (CT), where the relevant information is typically available with millimeter resolution.

There are several limitations to 3D tomography, common to many experimental techniques and length scales. Firstly, the resolution achieved must be sufficient for extracting the desired information, but it is often limited by the measuring technique and the necessity to keep the acquisition time short. For instance, in a CT scan one wants to have enough details to inform a medical decision, but limit the radiation dose the patient is exposed to [4]. Furthermore, in several cases the measurement is destructive, meaning that the specimen being imaged is destroyed during the measurement process [5, 6]. In this situation the 3D resolution is often anisotropic, meaning that cubic-voxel definition in the three dimensions is not achieved. In addition, in a destructive experiment one cannot go back and take a second measurement, should the first have not achieved enough resolution. The crucial question is then whether or not an image augmentation method may help in enhancing the image quality, in terms of resolution, thus enabling the extraction of more precise information. Should this be possible, one can also revert the question and establish which experimental conditions will be enabled by an image-augmentation method achieving the same information content than the non-corrected measurement. In order to understand better these issues, let us consider the specific case of FIB-SEM nanotomography (FIB-SEM-NT), where the term nano refers to the length scale involved [5]. This is a destructive imaging technique, where a focused-ion beam (FIB) mills away slices of a specimen, often a composite, while a scanning electron microscope (SEM) takes images of the exposed planes. The typical outcome is a stack of hundreds of 2D images, used to produce a high-fidelity 3D reconstruction. The resolution of the resulting 3D volume is often anisotropic, especially when working at high resolution. In fact, while the cross-section (also referred to as the xy-plane) is imaged at the SEM resolution, about 5 nm in our case, the resolution along the milling direction (the z-direction) corresponds to the slice thickness and it is usually around 10-20 nm. As a consequence, the reconstructed 3D volume will not be characterized by cubic voxels. Note that cutting thinner slices is hindered by the instrumentation, the nature of the specimen and by economic constraints.

78 Moreover, a reduction of the slice thickness implies a detriment of the resolu-
79 tion in the xy-plane, since the damage produced during one cut can propagate
80 to the following one. This limitation is linked to another problem of FIB-
81 SEM instruments, namely the slow imaging speed [7]. One would then desire
82 a method to interpolate images, which preserves and possibly enhances the
83 information quality and ideally reduces the number of milling steps to perform.

84 The simplest solution is linear interpolation [8]. However, this is reliable
85 only when one can safely assume that the structural variations across con-
86 secutive cross-sections are smooth. Unfortunately, when this condition is only
87 approximately met, linear interpolation tends to blur feature edges. This can
88 be partially improved [9] with interpolation strategies that account for feature
89 changes among consecutive images by using optical flow [10], but the perfor-
90 mance remains poor at the image borders. As a consequence, such portions of
91 the frame must be discarded, with a consequent loss of valuable information.
92 Alternative solutions involve deep-learning algorithms. For instance, Hagita
93 *et al.* [11] proposed a deep-learning-based method for super-resolution of 3D
94 images with asymmetric sampling. The model was trained on images obtained
95 from the cross-section and applied to frames co-planar to the milling direction
96 and obtained from the 3D reconstruction. Unfortunately, this strategy works
97 only when it is possible to assume that the three directions have the same mor-
98 phology, but does not provide unbiased reconstruction. In a different effort,
99 Dahari *et al.* [12] developed a generative adversarial network (GAN) trained on
100 pairs of high-resolution 2D images and low-resolution 3D data, aiming at gen-
101 erating a super-resolved 3D volume. The scheme showed success on a variety
102 of datasets. However, generative models are ambiguous to use in this context,
103 since they do not allow one to find a unique solution, due to the nature of this
104 deep-learning architecture.

105 Here, we propose an alternative solution that relies on the use of a deep-
106 learning model trained for video-frame interpolation. This is a process, where
107 the frame per second of a video is increased by generating additional frames
108 between the existing ones, thus creating a more visually fluid motion [13]. Com-
109 mon applications include the generation of slow-motion videos [14] and video
110 predictions [15]. Video-frame interpolation can be considered as a combination
111 of both enhancement and reconstruction technology. In fact, it enhances the
112 perceptual quality of a video by providing smoother and more natural motion.
113 At the same time, it can be designated as a form of video reconstruction,
114 since it aims at reconstructing the temporal evolution of a scene. Several deep-
115 learning frameworks have been proposed for this task. The state-of-the-art
116 algorithm is the Real-Time Intermediate Flow Estimation (RIFE) [16], which
117 will be extensively used here. The selected video-frame interpolation method,
118 like any neural network developed for this purpose, is inherently bound by cer-
119 tain limitations. It is important to note that such networks are constrained by
120 the information contained in the frames provided. The limitations associated
121 with the chosen video-frame interpolation method have been studied in the

122 original paper [16] and are anticipated to be transferable to any dataset under
123 investigation.

124 We begin by considering a dataset made of printed graphene-nanosheet
125 images, obtained with FIB-SEM, where the milling direction is taken as cor-
126 respondent to the video time direction. The resolution of this dataset is then
127 improved by the application of RIFE, and quantitatively validated using several
128 approaches. In particular, together with standard computer-vision metrics, we
129 evaluate physical quantities, which can be extracted from the final 3D recon-
130 structions, after appropriate image binarisation with standard software such as
131 FIJI [17] or DRAGONFLY [18]. These are the porosity, tortuosity, and effective
132 diffusivity, and their precise evaluation allows us to understand what informa-
133 tion content is preserved during the interpolation. Then, the same scheme is
134 applied, at a completely different length scale, to both MRI and CT scans. In
135 the first case, the 3D mapping is already isotropic, so that our reconstructed
136 images can be compared to an available ground truth, as in the case of FIB-
137 SEM. Instead, for CT scans we show a significant enhancement of the picture
138 quality, a result that may enable to reduce the scanning rate and therefore the
139 radiation dose for the patient.

140 Importantly, these are only some illustrative applications of the proposed
141 strategy, which could be useful in many other fields. Some examples include in-
142 situ electron microscopy [19], such as transmission electron microscopy (TEM)
143 and scanning-TEM. In this context, a reduction of recorded frames is crucial
144 to minimize the beam dose and therefore the possible beam-induced damage
145 to the specimen, and may allow to reduce the number of tilt images taken to
146 obtain a tomographic TEM reconstruction. In this work we demonstrate the
147 applicability of a neural network developed for video frame interpolation, in
148 contexts different from its original purpose. In particular, we employ this neural
149 network to ameliorate the acquisition conditions of 3D tomography across
150 different length scales. Throughout this work we compare our algorithm to
151 alternative interpolation strategies, demonstrating its quantitative advantage.

152 2 Results

153 The first test was conducted on a dataset made of printed nanostructured
154 graphene networks, described in the Methods section. In order to prove the
155 method’s efficacy, some frames are removed from the dataset and used as
156 ground truth for results assessment. We consider different scenarios, where
157 one, three and seven consecutive frames are removed from the image sequence,
158 although the seven-frame error suggests that it is not advisable to reduce so
159 drastically the image density along the milling direction. A simple visual com-
160 parison offers a qualitative overview of the efficacy of the various interpolation
161 methods. This is shown in Fig. 1 for the case where three consecutive frames
162 are removed from our FIB-SEM sequence and then reconstructed by the dif-
163 ferent models. The first column shows the ground-truth image, namely that

Fig. 1: Visual comparison of image interpolation according to different methods. Images from the FIB-SEM dataset are augmented using different approaches. In particular, three additional frame are generated every two consecutive frames in the sequence. From left to right we show: the ground truth image (original FIB-SEM), and those reconstructed by RIFE HD, the fine-tuned RIFE_m, DAIN, ISOFLOW, and linear interpolation. The second row displays the difference between the ground truth and the reconstructions. A 120×120 -pixel portion of each image (see green box in the upper left panel) is magnified and shown in the third row, while the differences from the original image are in the fourth row.

164 removed from the original dataset, while the remaining ones contain the pic-
 165 tures reconstructed with the various methods. In order to appreciate better
 166 the quality of the reconstructions, we also provide the difference between the
 167 ground truth and the reconstructed images (second row), the magnification of
 168 a 120×120 -pixel portion of each picture (third row), and again the difference
 169 from their ground truth (fourth row). The differences are obtained by simply
 170 subtracting the greyscale bitmap of each pixel. Blue (red) regions mean that
 171 the reconstructed image appears lighter (darker) than the original one.

172 The inspection of the figure leads to some qualitative considerations on the
 173 different methods, and the comparison is particularly clear for the magnified
 174 images. The most notable feature is the loss of sharpness brought by the linear
 175 interpolation, which is not motion aware. In fact, instead of tracing the motion
 176 of the border between a graphene nanosheet and a pore, namely the border
 177 region between dark and bright pixels, linear interpolation simply fills the space

178 with an average grayscale. As a result, the image differences (e.g. see the right-
 179 most lower panel) present some dipolar distribution, which, as we will show
 180 below, causes information loss. A similar, although less pronounced, drawback
 181 is found for images reconstructed by DAIN, which also tends to over-smooth the
 182 graphene borders. In contrast, ISOFLOW appears to generate generally good-
 183 quality pictures, in particular in the middle of the frame. However, one can
 184 clearly notice a significant error appearing at the image border, which is not
 185 well reproduced and whose information thus needs to be discarded. Finally,
 186 the two RIFE models are clearly the best-performing ones. Of similar quality,
 187 they are able to maintain the original image sharpness across the entire field
 188 of view and do not seem to show any systematic failure. Although instructive,
 189 visual inspection just provides a qualitative understanding, but more quanti-
 190 tative metrics need to be evaluated in order to determine what image content
 191 is preserved by the various reconstructions.

192 **2.1 Quantitative assessment of the extracted information** 193 **content**

194 A full quantitative analysis is better performed on segmented images, where the
 195 pore and nanosheet components are well separated [5]. This can be obtained
 196 by using the trainable WEKA segmentation tool [20] available in FIJI [17]. The
 197 procedure to produce binarised data is demonstrated in Fig. 2. A set of images
 198 from the original dataset is used to train a model, whose goal is to classify
 199 each pixel of the image either as pore or as nanosheet. The training set is
 200 automatically built by WEKA following the manual identification of pore and
 201 nanosheet areas from the user. This is shown in Fig. 2(a), where the red circles
 202 identify pixels that are labeled as pores and the green circles represent pixels
 203 labeled as nanosheets. Panel (b) of the same figure displays the outcome of the
 204 application of the trained model, where the grayscale expresses the probability
 205 of each pixel being labeled as pore or nanosheet. This is called a probability
 206 map. Finally, a threshold is applied to obtain a binary classification, as shown
 207 in Fig. 2(c). In particular, here the ISODATA algorithm [21], available in FIJI,
 208 is used to select an appropriate threshold.

209 Once the classifier is trained and the threshold is established, all the
 210 datasets obtained from the different interpolation strategies can be binarised.
 211 It should be noted that the performance of the classifier depends on the man-
 212 ual selection performed by the user. However, using the same classifier for
 213 all the analysed datasets guarantees consistency in the segmentation process
 214 and, consequently, in the quantitative assessment of the various reconstruction
 215 methods.

216 The Mean Square Error (MSE) and the Structure Similarity Index Method
 217 (SSIM) are some of the standard metrics used in computer vision to evaluate
 218 results [22]. Both are full-reference metrics, meaning that the ground truth
 219 is required to assess their value. The MSE focuses on the pixel-by-pixel com-
 220 parison and not on the structure of the image, while SSIM performs better
 221 in discriminating the structural information of the frames. Here the MSE is

Fig. 2: WEKA image binarisation procedure. Different phases of the procedure used to segment each frame into pore and nanosheet components. This generates binarised data, by using the trainable WEKA segmentation plugin of FIJI [5, 20]. In panel (a) the user first manually assigns the label of pore (red circles) and nanosheet (green circles) to some areas of the original image. This information is used to build the dataset for training a classifier, whose output is the probability map displayed in panel (b). Here the probability of each pixel being either pore or nanosheet is displayed using pixel intensity values. Panel (c) shows the final output of the procedure, namely the binarised image, obtained by applying a threshold on the probability map.

222 calculated between each of the generated frames and the corresponding image
 223 removed from the original dataset. The average of these values is then com-
 224 puted for each case of study (one, three, and seven replaced frames) and for
 225 each technique (RIFE HD, RIFE_m, DAIN, ISOFLOW and linear interpolation),
 226 for a set of 100 images. The same procedure is followed for the evaluation of
 227 the SSIM and our results are available in panel a and b of Fig. 3. As expected,
 228 all models perform better when the number of removed frames remains lim-
 229 ited, and in general there is a significant loss in performance for the case
 230 of seven replaced frames. In more detail, RIFE-type schemes are always the
 231 top performer, with linear interpolation, and also DAIN, remaining the most
 232 problematic. Interestingly, ISOFLOW appears quite accurate according to these
 233 computer-vision metrics, which clearly do not emphasize much the loss of res-
 234 olution at the frame boundary. However, we will now see that this does not
 235 necessarily translate into the ability to preserve information.

236 Ultimately, the quality of a reconstruction procedure must be measured
 237 with the quality of the information that is able to transfer/retrieve. In the
 238 case of printed graphene-nanosheet ensembles, the morphological properties
 239 can be measured and compared. The so-called network porosity, P , defined as
 240 the percentage of the total volume occupied by the pores, is one of the most
 241 important features measured in 2D networks and it affects the material electri-
 242 cal properties [23]. In our image-segmented 3D reconstruction this translates
 243 into the fraction of pores surface in each image, a quantity that can be evalu-
 244 ated from the binarised images by the conventional image-processing software
 245 FIJI [17]. Such analysis is performed here for each case of study and technique.
 246 In particular, from the binarised data the porosity of each frame is computed
 247 as $P=(\text{pores pixels})/(\text{total pixels})$.

Fig. 3: Evaluation of MSE, SSIM and porosity on binarised data. Mean Squared Error (MSE - panel a), Structural Similarity Index Method (SSIM - panel b) and Porosity (P - panel c) evaluated for each test case (one, three, and seven replaced frames) and each interpolation method, for 100 images. MSE and SSIM are evaluated for each frame against the ground truth and they are expressed as an average over the 100 frames. P is also evaluated for each frame against the ground truth and it is expressed in terms of ΔP [see Eq. (1)], namely as a percentage deviation from the ground-truth value. For each panel, the average value is shown with the associated variance.

248 The results are then expressed in terms of delta porosity, ΔP , which is the
 249 fractional difference between the porosity computed from images reconstructed
 250 with a particular method m , P_m , and that of the ground truth, P_{GT} , namely

$$\Delta P = 100 * \frac{|P_m - P_{GT}|}{P_{GT}}. \quad (1)$$

251 In our case the ΔP of 100 images is computed and the average of these values
 252 is presented in panel c of Fig. 3. From the figure the advantage of using RIFE
 253 is quite clear. In fact, although all methods, except for the linear interpolation,
 254 give a faithful approximation of P when one frame is removed from the
 255 sequence, differences start to emerge already at three replaced frames, where
 256 RIFE significantly outperforms all other schemes. The difference becomes even
 257 more evident for seven replaced frames, for which the RIFE error remains sur-
 258 prisingly below 2%. Also, it is interesting to note that, in contrast to what is
 259 suggested by the computer-vision metrics, ISOFLOW is not capable of accu-
 260 rately returning a precise porosity, mainly because of the poor description of
 261 the image borders. In contrast, the weak performance of the linear interpo-
 262 lation has to be attributed to its inability to describe sharp borders between
 263 nanosheets and pores.

264 A second important structural feature that can be retrieved from nano-
 265 structured networks is the network tortuosity, τ , which can be evaluated on
 266 binarised data using the TAUFACOR software [24]. This quantity describes the
 267 effect that a convolution in the geometry of heterogeneous media has on diffu-
 268 sive transport and can be measured for both the nanosheet and pore volumes.

269 The nanosheet network tortuosity factor influences charge transport through
 270 the film. Pore tortuosity affects performance in nanosheet-based battery elec-
 271 trodes, while in gas sensing applications the pore tortuosity is directly linked
 272 to gas diffusion. The tortuosity, τ , and volume fraction, ε , of a phase are used
 273 to relate the reduction in the diffusive flux through that phase by comparing
 274 its effective diffusivity, D^{eff} , to the intrinsic diffusivity, D :

$$D^{\text{eff}} = D \frac{\varepsilon}{\tau}. \quad (2)$$

275 The TAUFACTOR software calculates the tortuosity from stacks of segmented
 276 images. Specifically, it employs an over-relaxed iterative method to determine
 277 the tortuosity. This approach is utilized for solving the steady-state diffusion
 278 equation governing the movement of species in an infinitely dilute solution
 279 within a porous medium confined by fixed-value boundaries. It has been proved
 280 that for the evaluation of the tortuosity and diffusivity the sample volume
 281 needs to be adequately large, in order to be representative of the bulk and to
 282 reduce the effect of microscopic heterogeneities [25]. For this reason, we con-
 283 sider ten randomly selected volumes, ranging from 55% to 60% of the original
 284 one. Such fraction has been chosen after performing a scaling analysis, namely
 285 by computing the tortuosity factor for different volumes and by noticing that
 286 the bulk limit was obtained at around 55% (see Supplementary Information).
 287 As the size of the input sample highly affects the computation speed and
 288 memory requirement, not all methods are considered for this comparison. In
 289 particular, only RIFE HD and DAIN results are used as input for the tortuosity
 290 and diffusivity study. These two methods are chosen since they provide the
 291 best evaluation of the porosity. Then, the Python version of TAUFACTOR [26]
 292 is run on Quadro RTX 8000 GPUs.

293 Also in this case we compute the fractional change of any given quantity
 294 from the ground truth, and the results are displayed in Fig. 4. Confirming the
 295 results obtained for ΔP also in this case RIFE is the best-performing method,
 296 with errors remaining below 2% at three replaced frames for both τ and D^{eff} .
 297 In contrast, DAIN displays significant errors, exceeding 10%, already for a single
 298 replaced frame, an error that suggested analysis at other replaced-frame rates
 299 was unnecessary.

300 Analysing the properties outlined in this section is an essential aspect for all
 301 applications involving transport in heterogeneous media, influenced by geom-
 302 etry. For instance, in the field of catalysis, the mentioned properties are used
 303 to determine the extent of accessibility to the nanosheet surface area.

304 2.2 Dependence on the features size

305 As demonstrated in the previous section our method performs well at recon-
 306 structing the frames of the FIB-SEM sequence, with errors on physically
 307 relevant quantities remaining below 10% even for seven replaced frames. This
 308 is equivalent to having a milling thickness of about 100 nm, indeed a very
 309 favorable experimental condition. In this section, we discuss the limitations

Fig. 4: Evaluation of tortuosity and effective diffusivity on binarised data. Delta tortuosity, $\Delta\tau$ (panel a), and delta effective diffusivity, ΔD^{eff} (panel b), evaluated for each test case (one, three, and seven replaced frames) for RIFE HD, and for one replaced frame for the DAIN interpolation. The metrics are evaluated for each frame against the ground truth and averaged over the sequence. The variance is also displayed, and in the case of RIFE it is smaller than the symbols size.

of our approach in relation to the type of sample to investigate. A relevant problem with image interpolation techniques concerns the level of continuity between consecutive frames. In fact, it is well understood that rapid changes between the images in a sequence can reduce the quality of the interpolated frames [13]. The same issue may arise when considering FIB-SEM measurements of graphene nanosheets of different lengths. In this case, shorter nanosheets will result in FIB-SEM images with more abrupt changes between consecutive frames. For instance, if the average nanosheet length is L and the milling distance L' , for $L \sim L'$ one will encounter often the situation where a nanosheet present in one image will not appear in the next one.

In order to explore how the proposed model works with increasingly challenging datasets, we investigate the case networks made of shorter graphene nanosheets, namely of 80 nm and 298 nm in length (these are the average lengths). Examples of such networks, together with the original one of 695 nm can be found in Fig. 5. In this case, we use ΔP as evaluation criterion and consider three replaced frames, together with the original RIFE HD model. Our results can be found in Fig. 6, where we show ΔP against the average nanosheet length. For this comparison, the data are binarised following the procedure described in the previous section and ΔP is computed as an average over 100 images. It is evident from the figure, as expected, that the performance of our model indeed deteriorates when reducing the nanosheet's length. However, even for the smallest sample, 80 nm, the error remains below a very acceptable 2%. Note that in these conditions (nanosheet length 80 nm and three replaced frames, equivalent to ~ 50 nm milling distance) the milling distance is about half of the average feature size of the sample. Since networks made of small flakes are certainly structurally more fragile than those made with larger

Fig. 5: Illustration of graphene nanosheets of different lengths. Cross-sections of printed graphene nanosheets of different lengths (L). The nanosheet length decreases going from the top panel to the bottom one. In each case the image width shown is 6510 nm.

336 ones, the fact that the milling frequency can be reduced significantly without
 337 a sensible loss in the accuracy of the morphology determination, establishes
 338 a possible new experimental condition, where the milling effects on the final
 morphology are strongly minimised.

Fig. 6: Investigation of the feature size dependence. Porosity evaluated for the three replaced frames case, for different nanosheet lengths (80 nm, 298 nm and 695 nm). The porosity is evaluated for each frame generated by RIFE HD against the ground truth and it is expressed in terms of ΔP [see Eq. (1)]. Here we show the average ΔP over 100 images and the associated variance.

2.3 Application to medical datasets

The strategy proposed in this work is not limited to FIB-SEM generated data, but can be employed to increase the through-plane resolution of datasets of materials at different scales, obtained by using different imaging instruments. The purpose of this section is exactly to show such transfer across scales, and for this reason, we did not perform any additional training or fine-tuning of the original model. As such we now consider only RIFE HD. The first example is an application of RIFE to human brain MRI scans. For this dataset, the voxels of the reconstructed volume are already cubic with a 1 mm^3 resolution. However, this is a useful case study, since it is possible to remove frames from the scan sequence and use them as ground truth for the validation, as in the case of FIB-SEM. In particular, we remove every other frame from the original dataset, which has been downloaded from the Brainstorm repository [27, 28]. This is well documented and freely available online for download under the GNU general public license. For this study, we consider brain scans in the sagittal view as input for HD RIFE.

A visual comparison of one original and the corresponding RIFE-generated slice in the sagittal view is shown in the first row of Fig. 7 (panels a, b, c), where the patient was defaced to fulfill privacy requirements. The third column (panels c and f) of the mentioned figure shows the difference between the original and the generated image. Clearly, the visual inspection of the reconstructed image appears very positive with a difference from the ground truth (see top right panel), which presents an error similar to that of the FIB-SEM data, despite the rather different length scale, and little structure in its distribution.

The BRAINSUITE software [29] is then used to quantitatively compare the original and the RIFE-generated volumes, again trying to understand whether the information content is preserved. More specifically, the Anatomical pipeline is performed on both stacks to obtain the full brain segmentation, whose output is shown in the axial view in panels d and e of Fig. 7. Also in this case the visual inspection is similar to that made for the original images, with similar error characteristics. These segmentations are then used to evaluate the gray-matter volume variation (GMV), a widely used metric for the investigation of brain disorders such as Alzheimer’s disease [30, 31]. This is defined as,

$$\text{GMV} = \frac{p_{\text{gray}}}{p_{\text{gray}} + p_{\text{white}}}, \quad (3)$$

where p_{gray} and p_{white} indicate the number of gray and white pixels, respectively. The percentage error between the GMV of the two datasets is computed to be 0.5 %, again very low.

The final medical application investigated here refers to CT scans. Note that this measurement technique is not limited to the medical space, but it is also widely used in industrial settings and in general as a research tool across materials science [32]. The use of interpolation methods for medical CT could be really transformative, since a reduction of the collected frames

Fig. 7: Application of RIFE to a MRI dataset. An example of the original and the corresponding RIFE-generated frame in the sagittal view is shown in panels a and b, respectively. Panel c displays the intensity difference between the ground truth and the RIFE-generated images. The two datasets are segmented by using the Anatomical pipeline of the BRAINS SUITE software, as displayed in the second row. The original and corresponding RIFE-generated data are shown in panel d and e, respectively, while panel f presents the difference between them. Although the results are here presented in axial view only, the segmentation is performed on the full volume.

382 translates into a reduction of the radiation dose delivered to the patient. As a
 383 consequence, the potential risk of radiation-induced cancer will diminish [33].
 384 Alternatively, one may have the possibility to perform more frequent scans for
 385 close monitoring of particular diseases. The dataset used for this investigation
 386 is downloaded from the Cancer Imaging Archive [34, 35] and is provided as a
 387 set of 152 frames in the axial view, with a pixel size of $0.74 \times 0.74 \times 2.49$ mm.
 388 For this example, the voxels in the reconstructed volume are not cubic and no
 389 ground truth is available. RIFE is then used to generate three additional frames
 390 between every two existing ones. The results can be seen in Fig. 8 and Fig. 9
 391 Fig. 8 show the data in axial view. Panel a show one of the original frames
 392 of the CT dataset, while panel b presents a frame generated with RIFE, using
 393 the former image as an input for the interpolation model. It is important to
 394 note that in this case, the two panels do not represent the same section of the
 395 body, therefore they can only be compared from a qualitative point of view.
 396 From this figure, we can only observe that RIFE is able to generate realistic
 397 representations of CT scans in the axial view. Fig. 9 displays the original and
 398 RIFE-augmented datasets in coronal view, on panel a and b, respectively. The
 399 original-sized data are shown in the first row, while the second row (panels c
 400 and d) presents 150×150 -pixels magnified portions of the data (indicated by

401 green boxes in the first row). The red and blue boxes are used for the noise
 402 power spectrum analysis that will be described shortly. For the coronal view,
 403 the comparative figure helps assess the improvement introduced by RIFE. This
 404 visual comparison appears quite favourable, with the RIFE reconstruction being
 405 in general smoother than the original image. This is, of course, the result of
 having more frames added to the sequence.

Fig. 8: Application of RIFE to an X-ray Computed Tomography dataset, axial view. Here the results are presented in the axial view, namely the view in which the original sequence, used as input for RIFE, is depicted. On the left-hand-side panel, there is one of the original frames from the CT dataset, while the right-hand-side panel displays a frame created using RIFE, with the former image serving as an input for the interpolation model. It is essential to emphasize that these two panels depict different sections of the body, allowing for only a qualitative comparison. This figure enables us to discern that RIFE effectively produces reasonable representations of CT scans in the axial view.

406
 407 Since no ground truth is available in this case, we need to resource to
 408 computer-vision metrics to provide a quantitative assessment of the recon-
 409 struction procedure. Therefore, the two image stacks, the original and the
 410 RIFE-reconstructed one, are compared by estimating the noise power spectrum
 411 on the coronal plane, computed over uniform regions of a sequence of ten
 412 images. This metric is generally used for the assessment of the image quality
 413 of CT scanners and it is evaluated over uniform regions of interest in water-
 414 filled phantoms [36]. As such, in order to adapt this metric to clinical datasets,
 415 it is necessary to select uniform areas of the image. For instance, the areas in
 416 Fig. 9 marked with the red and blue squares represent two possible regions of
 417 interest, here called ‘case 1’ and ‘case 2’, respectively. The noise power spec-
 418 trum of these areas, evaluated over a stack of ten frames, is shown in Fig. 10.
 419 From the analysis of both cases, it is evident that this time augmenting the
 420 number of frames using RIFE HD is associated with a reduction of the noise in
 421 the data, a reduction visible across the entire frequency range. This quantifies

Fig. 9: Application of RIFE to an X-ray Computed Tomography dataset, coronal view. Here the results are presented in the coronal view. Panel a displays the original dataset, while panel b show the RIFE-augmented dataset, where three additional frames have been added between every two consecutive frames. The green boxes in the first row of the figure indicate a 150×150 -pixels portion of the original-sized data that is magnified in the second row. The red (Case 1) and blue (Case 2) boxes represent the uniform regions used for the noise power spectrum analysis, whose results are presented in Fig. 10.

422 the original observation that RIFE-augmented images look smoother. The same
 423 consideration holds for other uniform regions that have been investigated.

424 It is worth mentioning that medical images undergo significant process-
 425 ing, which impacts how noise and resolution appear in the final results. This
 426 is influenced by several factors, such as image acquisition techniques, recon-
 427 struction methodologies, and any additional post-processing steps. Further
 428 improvements, achievable with different approaches, were not investigated in
 429 this work.

430 We wish to conclude this section by making two considerations concerning
 431 the augmentation of sequences of images in the medical domain. In general,
 432 this has two main issues. Firstly, one has to ensure that the quality of the
 433 reconstructed images in a sequence is very close to the quality of the physically
 434 acquired images, so that the information content in a sequence is preserved.

Fig. 10: Noise power spectrum analysis. Analysis of the noise power spectrum conducted over two uniform regions in the coronal view (see Fig. 9 for definition). The comparison is performed between the original and the RIFE-augmented dataset. The use of RIFE results in noise reduction for both the selected regions and across the entire frequency range. The first case is displayed in panel a and the second case is displayed in panel b.

435 Such test has been performed here for the FIB-SEM case, for which ground
 436 truth was available, but only partially for the medical examples. In fact, for
 437 the medical examples we were able just to evaluate computer-graphic metrics
 438 but not the information content, since no ground truth was accessible to us.
 439 Such test may certainly become possible in the future, initially, mostly likely,
 440 through real images taken with dummies. The second issue is significantly more
 441 complex, as one has to evaluate whether the enhanced tomography helps the
 442 practitioners to make better decisions. This is an issue that must be resolved
 443 through a tight collaboration with medical experts, who will provide their
 444 human judgment on the usefulness of the augmentation. The format of such
 445 evaluation has still to be developed, but it is certainly desirable to formulate a
 446 protocol for both the research and the regulatory environments. In absence of
 447 this, the deployment of AI-technology to the medical field will certainly remain
 448 at large.

449 3 Discussion

450 We have demonstrated that a state-of-the-art neural network, developed for
 451 video-frame interpolation, can be used to increase the resolution of image
 452 sequences in 3D tomography. This can be applied, without further training,
 453 across different length scales, going from a few nanometers to millimeters,
 454 and to the most diverse types of samples. As the main benchmark, we have
 455 considered a dataset of images of printed graphene nanostructured networks,
 456 obtained with the destructive FIB-SEM technique. For this, we have carefully
 457 evaluated computer-vision metrics, but most importantly the quality of the
 458 information content that can be extracted from the 3D reconstruction. In
 459 particular, we have computed the porosity, tortuosity, and effective diffusivity

of the original dataset. This was then compared to datasets where an increasing number of images were removed and replaced with computer-generated ones.

In general, we have found that motion-aware video-frame interpolation outperforms the other interpolation strategies we tested. In particular, we have shown that it is not prone to image blurring, typical of simple linear interpolation, or to resolution loss at the image boundaries, as shown by some hybrid optical-flow algorithms. This is due to the coarse-to-fine approach implemented within the RIFE model, which allows one to make accurate predictions both in terms of intermediate flow estimation and level of details, as demonstrated in the original paper for several datasets [16]. Most importantly, the error on the determination of morphological observables remains below 2% as long as the milling thickness is less than approximately half of the nanosheet length. This suggests a very favorable experimental condition, where the effects of the milling on the measured morphology are significantly mitigated.

Then, we have moved our analysis to datasets taken from the medical field. These include a 3D tomography of the human brain volume, acquired with magnetic resonance imaging, and the X-ray computed tomography of the human torso. In the first case a ground truth was available, and we have been able to show that the estimate of the gray-matter volume variation is only affected by 0.5%, when half of the images in a scan are replaced with video-frame interpolated ones. This suggests that the scan rate can be actually increased, saving in acquisition time. In contrast, for the CT scan no ground truth was available so that we have limited ourselves to estimating computer-vision metrics. In particular, we have shown that the augmentation of data with computer-interpolated images, in order to reach cubic-voxel resolution, improves the power spectrum of the tomographic reconstruction, confirming the visual impression of smoother images. This result may be potentially transformative, since it can pave the way for reduced scan rates, with the consequent reduction in the radiation dose to be administered to the patient.

In summary, we have shown that video-frame interpolation techniques can be successfully applied to 3D tomography regardless of the acquisition experimental technique and of the nature of the specimen to image. This can improve practices when radiation-dose damage or the acquisition time are issues limiting the applicability of the method.

4 Methods

4.1 Printed Graphene Network dataset

The main dataset used in this work contains 801 images, generated with FIB-SEM, of printed nanostructured graphene networks, with a nanosheet length of approximately 700 nm. Each image, made of 4041×510 pixels, has a 5 nm resolution in the cross-section, while the slice thickness is 15 nm. Therefore, the voxel size in the resulting reconstructed volume is $5 \times 5 \times 15 = 375 \text{ nm}^3$. Note that the voxel size achievable with conventional micro CT scanners is 10-1000 times larger [37, 38]. Therefore, FIB-SEM nanotomography is more

503 suitable than CT for the quantitative characterisation of the graphene network
504 morphology. Further details on sample preparation and data acquisition can
505 be found in [5].

506 A fraction of the original dataset is considered for the majority of the
507 analysis, so as to reduce the computational effort and to inspect the images in
508 more detail. Specifically, for the computer-vision metrics and porosity analysis,
509 100 images of the original dataset are considered. Each image of this subset
510 is cut to a 510×510 pixels size. In contrast, for the tortuosity and effective
511 diffusivity study, ten randomly selected volumes are considered, ranging from
512 55% to 60% of the original volume. It should be noted that in all cases the
513 resolution is not altered.

514 4.2 Neural Network

515 Five main methodologies are usually employed for video-frame interpolation,
516 namely flow-based methods, convolutional-neural-networks (CNN), phase-
517 based approaches, GANs, and hybrid schemes. These typically differ from
518 each other because of the network architecture and their mathematical founda-
519 tion [39]. RIFE [16] belongs to the flow-based category, whose focus is the
520 determination of the nature of the flow between corresponding elements in
521 consecutive frames. When compared to other popular algorithms [40–42], RIFE
522 performs better both in terms of accuracy and computational speed. Mod-
523 els belonging to this class usually involve a two-phase process: the warping of
524 input frames in accordance with the approximated optical flow and the use
525 of CNNs to combine and refine the warped frames. The outcome of the inter-
526 mediate flow estimation often requires the presence of additional components,
527 such as depth-estimation [40] and flow-refinement models [41], so to mitigate
528 potential inaccuracy. Unlike other methods, RIFE does not require supplement-
529 ary networks, a feature that significantly impacts the model speed. In fact,
530 the intermediate flow is learned end-to-end by a CNN. As demonstrated in
531 the original RIFE paper [16], learning the intermediate flow end-to-end can
532 reduce motion-modelling related inaccuracies. RIFE adopts a neural-network
533 architecture, IFNet, which directly estimates the intermediate flow adopting
534 a coarse-to-fine approach with progressively increased resolution. In particu-
535 lar, the first step is an approximated prediction of the intermediate flow on
536 low resolution. This allows one to capture large motions between consecu-
537 tive frames. Subsequently the prediction is refined iteratively, by considering
538 frames with gradually increased resolution, a procedure that allows the model
539 to retain fine details in the interpolated frame. This approach guarantees
540 accurate results, both in terms of flow estimation and level of details in the
541 generated frame. Moreover, a privileged distillation scheme is introduced to
542 train the model. Specifically, a teacher model with access to the ground-truth
543 intermediate frame refines the student model performance. The input of the
544 RIFE model can either be a video or a sequence of two images. For this project,
545 the most straightforward solution is to use images. Therefore, we have adapted
546 the model to accept a series of any number of images, instead of only two at

547 a time. The new version of the inference file of the code can be found at the
 548 link provided in this manuscript. Although the model is trained on RGB data,
 549 it can seamlessly handle grayscale images, as this functionality is inherently
 550 embedded in the original code. Specifically, the images are loaded using an
 551 OPENCV [43] flag, which ensures that they are loaded as grayscale data. As
 552 with any large machine-learning model, RIFE updates regularly. At the cur-
 553 rent moment in time, the best version available is the HD model v4.6, referred
 554 to as RIFE HD [44]. This is trained on the Vimeo90K dataset, which covers a
 555 large variety of scenes and actions, involving people, animals, and objects [45].
 556 As the training set is remarkably different from the application cases of this
 557 work, we perform fine-tuning of the available pre-trained model, on Quadro
 558 RTX 8000 GPUs, provided by Nvidia. Since fine-tuning of RIFE HD is cur-
 559 rently not possible, the second-best model is here considered, namely RIFE_m
 560 [46]. The fine-tuning is then performed on a subset of the graphene dataset,
 561 made of 1,000 portions of the original images, cropped to a 510×510 -pixel
 562 size and not used for testing. The instructions provided by the RIFE code
 563 developers are followed to perform the fine tuning, with some small code mod-
 564 ifications. The modified training file can be found in the provided repository.
 565 The results of both the original and the fine-tuned model are presented in
 566 the following section and compared throughout. Furthermore, we benchmark
 567 our scheme against another flow-based deep-learning algorithm, DAIN [40], and
 568 against non-deep-learning methods. In particular, we consider the simple but
 569 widely used linear interpolation and the ISOFLOW algorithm [9], an interpo-
 570 lation technique that takes into consideration the variation among slices by
 571 using optical flow [10].

572 In closing, we note that here we have explored the current state of the art in
 573 video-frame interpolation. Certainly, one can also expect that our results will
 574 further improve as newer and more accurate machine-learning architectures
 575 for video-frame interpolation become available.

576 **Data availability.** The data that support the findings of this study are avail-
 577 able from the corresponding author upon request. Source data are provided
 578 with this paper.

579 **Code availability.** The main code used for this project, developed by Huang
 580 et al., can be found at [44, 46]. Some minor changes were made to this code, the
 581 modified version is available at: [https://github.com/StefanoSanvitoGroup/](https://github.com/StefanoSanvitoGroup/RIFE-3D-tom)
 582 [RIFE-3D-tom](https://github.com/StefanoSanvitoGroup/RIFE-3D-tom) [47].

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760 and the calculation of porosity, tortuosity and intrinsic diffusivity. C.G., L.D.,
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762 the relative data. P.G. provided support with the medical-data analysis. S.S.
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